

CHEMOTHERAPY OF MALARIA

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The preparation of some 5-thiolacridine derivatives is described.

Of all the acridine derivatives, those which contain a dialkylamino-alkylamino group in 5 position possess strongest antimalarial properties. Atebrin (I), which is a compound of this type, is very effectively used in malaria. It possesses strong antiseptic action against all asexual forms of malarial parasites (Kikuth, *Deut. Med. Wochs.*, 1932, 63, 530; Magidson and Grigorowski, *Ber.*, 1936, 69, 396; Mauss and Mietzsch, *Klin. Wochs.*, 12, 1276).

Recently the author described a number of 5-thiolacridine compounds which may be regarded as the sulphur analogues of 5-aminoacridines (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 244). From an examination of the compounds of type (I) it is evident that the addition of a dialkylaminoalkyl group to the 5-aminoacridines develops remarkable antimalarial properties. So it was contemplated that the addition of the same group i.e. dialkylaminoalkyl to the 5-thiolacridines may develop antimalarial or other chemotherapeutic properties. Hence an investigation has been undertaken to synthesise a number of compounds of type (II) and to study their chemotherapeutic properties. Several of such compounds have already been prepared and as expected have been found to possess strong antiseptic action against paramacia. The experimental results on paramacia will be described elsewhere.

The compounds are low melting and have, therefore, been isolated as hydrochlorides which are highly soluble in water. The molecular weights of these compounds are favourable for an antimalarial drug (*cf.* Slotta and Behnisch, *Ber.*, 1935, 68, 754).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5-(β -diethylaminoethyl) thioacridine. — 2 G. of 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thiolacridine (Das-Gupta, *loc. cit*) was heated with β -diethylaminoethyl bromide hydrobromide (5 g.) in phenol (10 g.) containing 3-4 g. of sodium hydroxide 100-110° for 3 hours. The mixture was poured into dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with dilute acetic acid. The acetic acid solution after being shaken with ether, was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution and again extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and evaporated, when a viscous liquid was obtained. This was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid in cold. On concentrating the acid solution in vacuum small orange-yellow rectangular needles of the dihydrochloride

were obtained. This was further crystallised from alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 223°. (Found: N, 6'4; Cl, 23'6. $C_{20}H_{22}ClN_2S$, 2HCl requires N, 6'25; Cl, 23'8 per cent).

7-Methoxy-5-(β-diethylaminoethyl)thioacridine was prepared from 7-methoxy-5-thioacridine and β-diethylaminoethyl bromide hydrobromide, exactly in the same way as in the previous case. The dihydrochloride was finally obtained as orange-yellow needles, m.p. 209-10°. (Found: Cl, 17'14; S, 7'96. $C_{20}H_{24}ON_2S$, 2HCl requires, Cl, 17'19; S, 7'74 per cent).

2-Chloro-7-methoxy-5 (γ-diethylaminopropyl)thioacridine was prepared from 2-chloro-7-methoxy-5-thioacridine (1 mol.) and γ-diethylaminopropyl chloride (1.2 mol.) by heating in phenol at 110-120° for several hours. After treatment of the reaction mixture as in the previous cases, the dihydrochloride was obtained as orange-yellow needles from alcohol-ether mixture, m.p. 195-97°. (Found: N, 5'89. $C_{21}H_{28}ON_2ClS$, 2 HCl requires N, 6'07 per cent).

7-Methoxy-5-(γ-diethylaminopropyl)thioacridine was prepared from 7-methoxy-5-thioacridine and γ-diethylaminopropyl chloride in the same way as before and the dihydrochloride was obtained as orange-yellow needles, m.p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 6'34. $C_{21}H_{28}ON_2S$, 2 HCl requires N, 6'56 per cent).

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